

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: This article talks about foreign language teaching methodology, modern methods used in foreign language teaching methodology, their use and what results can be achieved through these methods.

Key words: method, innovative, technology, student, foreign language, the case study method, communicative method

Language is one of the means of knowing and communicating with the surrounding world. In particular, a foreign language has a special place in the modern education system due to its social, cognitive and developmental functions. The development of world science is developing day by day, the position of the English language in international communication in the world is becoming stronger, and taking into account this process, the problem of using effective methods in this regard is set. Teaching and learning English is considered very important, and advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. At the same time, modern educational development requires innovative pedagogy. Innovative that means, action or innovation process, new method, idea and product in English. Innovation is a process in which education, a new method develops with certain stages. The application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the field of education has opened the door to wide opportunities and conveniences for young people learning a foreign language.

Learning a new language may be challenging. For some people it seems natural, however for many it's more of a struggle, and rather a long and difficult process. Luckily, there is no single method of teaching English that is always right. How to choose the right method of teaching English? Over the years different science, theories, and learning styles were developed in terms of teaching foreign languages. You won't find the best, the one and only method of teaching English to kids or adults. Choosing the proper teaching style depends on students' skills and abilities. The learning process is a complex process that involves, first of all, the mutual activity of the teacher and the activity of students. In modern conditions it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of students' creative abilities, their cognitive needs and interests. Also, with the right motivation to learn English, the students are more likely to

succeed. So in order to choose the right method of teaching English to adults or children, start with understanding why a person needs or wants to learn the language and then focus on the best technique to achieve their goal. Teaching as a guide involves the presentation, communication by the teacher of certain knowledge and management of the process of mastering it by all students of the class. Therefore, the teacher not only presents information on his subject, but also plans, organizes and controls the student's educational activities, develops the skills of educational work, thinking, abilities, and also the ability to apply knowledge in practice.

A special place in solving these problems belongs to the methods and techniques of teaching, which every teacher should be able to use competently. Without methods and techniques, it is impossible to achieve the set goal, implement the intended content and fill the training with cognitive activity. At the present stage of education, a modern teacher will prefer to use well-known innovative methods that show high efficiency in learning a foreign language. Using new forms of learning, the teacher increases the student's interest and his desire to continue learning in cognitive matter, considers each in detail and determines the features of learning. What are the best ways to learn a foreign language? English can be learned effectively in the following ways:

A Task-based approach

A task-based approach to teaching English isolates individual skills and competencies to teach students what they really need to know in order to achieve their goals and objectives. Tasks in this method should be based on common real situations that a student may encounter, such as being on vacation, talking to foreigners at a hotel, airport, or restaurant. Thus, a task-based approach is to teach advanced tasks such as how to order a meal at a restaurant, how to book a hotel room, or how to critique a theater play.

Belongs to the project

Another way to teach English is to base the installation process on customization and usage. The method is safe for high school students and professional adults, but in the last 10 years, teachers have also carried out carrying in younger children and preschoolers. Project Method. It helps to develop language skills and creative thinking. After completing each topic, students must work on it and "defend" it by speaking about its content in English. For example, to discuss topics such as "my favorite food", "my pet..." or "I have..." in my house, children have the opportunity to talk about things that are important to them. Armed with graphics and photos, this is a very

interesting and fun way to practice English, making it easier to remember new vocabulary and phrases.

The Gamification method

Gamification is the most common way to engage children and facilitate learning. When children play games, they are in their baggage, they take to it like a duck to water. The games are attractive both in terms of organization and content.

Each game has a place where you need to follow, which helps to develop organization. All children know their set rules. Games allow children to move, interact, share things, etc. gives and being active is natural for children. In terms of content, learning is beneficial because you can learn any content from them. For children, learning is learning, they memorize words quickly and can even use them spontaneously in their speech. Any game ended like real life for kids! Only the teacher knows how didactic and linguistically demanding it is.

Theatricalization or dramatization

Theater in English is a favorite teaching method of many teachers and a favorite activity of many students. Children especially will immerse themselves in the world of brave princes and princesses, evil witches and good fairies, magical creatures and talking animals. Children are quickly attracted to the plot and remember the events, favorite characters and catchy phrases of the file.

a pre-service teacher can read a story and discuss it with students, look at pictures or watch a cartoon, learn key words and later "tell" the story. But what children like most is to watch the performances of their favorite scenes or fairy tales with puppets, screens and decorations. Play preparation immerses students in an English-speaking environment and leaves the language more natural. Therefore, when speaking with children in English, the "immersion method" immediately helps to develop language visibility, them and contextual resources in English. It is for this reason that it is very popular among teachers who teach English to children.

Currently, we can note five main types of foreign language teaching that are used all over the world, but few people know about them: case method, communicative method, silent method,

The case study method is a method of active analysis of a problem situation based on learning by solving specific situational problems. The essence of the case method: students divided into groups must analyze the situation and develop a practical solution; the end of the process is to evaluate the proposed algorithms and discuss them in the context of the general discussion. This

method is used in foreign language classes in classical education, where students are presented with a real-life problem situation that they have to solve based on existing knowledge, practical experience and intuition. Since there is more than one solution to any situation, all possible solutions are discussed.

The communicative method is the most popular of the modern methods of learning foreign languages. This method is the most active for learning a foreign language, because the main purpose of this method is to teach a person to communicate with other people in the target language, which means all forms of communication: speech, writing (reading and writing skills), the ability to listen and understand what the interlocutor says. If the student is literally "immersed" in the environment of the language being studied and its main aspects, it will be much easier to achieve improvement in learning factors. The communicative method is suitable for almost every student, because it allows you to learn a foreign language faster and more consciously.

The silent way - according to this method, the initial knowledge of any foreign language is a priori unique to a person, and he alone can achieve the required level of knowledge. In this method, the teacher does not say any words in the language being studied so as not to confuse the students with their subjective perception of the language. When teaching pronunciation, the teacher uses special charts in which each color or symbol represents a specific sound, thereby introducing new words. Thus, knowledge of the language is formed at the level of the system of conditional interactions, up to the subconscious, which, according to the authors, should lead to bright results.

Audio-lingual method - this method is not ideal from the point of view of teaching, because it is based on compression. Training is based on the principle: heard-repeated. The teacher says the phrase; the student must repeat it accurately until the pronunciation reaches a certain level. Only then the student has the right to add words and details.

Using these methods will help to develop the following aspects:

- formation of positive educational motivation throughout the process;
- increasing cognitive activity of each student;
- assimilation of a large amount of educational information;
- reveal personal and individual, universal possibilities of each student;
- to determine the conditions for their manifestation and development.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted teaching, in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, it compares the mother tongue and foreign language through various methods and technologies.

Methods and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. The most effective way to master all knowledge is repetition and practice. In order to learn a foreign language well, first of all, the learner should have an interest and purpose in this language. Also, if one method causes difficulties for the learner to learn a foreign language, it is necessary to try other modern methods and modern technologies without stopping language learning. The most important thing is not to give up. We should not surrender to science, we should subjugate it.

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